

Jhumpa Lahiri and Kiran Desai, The New Women Diasporic Writers

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: October

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2321-788X

E-ISSN: 2582-0397

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Hemalatha, C. "Jhumpa Lahiri and Kiran Desai, The New Women Diasporic Writers." *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 177–80.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3549302>

C. Hemalatha

*Research Scholar and Guest Lecturer
Department of English, Government Arts and Science College
Kottur, Theni*

Abstract

Kiran Desai and Jhumpa Lahiri, the new women writers, who have enriched the genre of Indian English fiction but their imagination goes beyond the boundaries of their gender. They address themselves to an Indian culture in which there is a social pain and cultural displacement within the country as well as outside the country because of globalization and immigration. They voice the agony of the Indian immigrants settled in alien land with full of feelings on many fronts. The reasons for choosing these two critically acclaimed and award winning writers are many as these two writers contemporary and have so many similarities and dissimilarities. They have so many commonalities and also inherent differences which is both overt and covert. The treatment of women characters in the immigrant stories also demand a close look at the fictional works of Lahiri and Desai.

Keywords: Diaspora, Jhumpa Lahiri, Kiran Desai.

Diaspora Writings

The 1980s brought forth the sudden spirit of creative writing and the sense of awareness of the plurality of the nation. The fine work of art, the fictions, the other forms of creative works brought out the east – west conflict and portrays the new Post-Colonial India with its evolving outlook, which is essentially a blend of tradition and modernism. It reveals the cosmopolitan outlook of the new generation who strives to strike a balance between the inherited traditional values and imbibed foreign culture. Trans-national and Trans-continental in nature, the modern authors were successful in every aspect. Writers such as Salman Rushdie, the Man Booker Prize winner, Amitav Ghosh and Upamanya Chatterjee are the writers who published books of international repute. The three authors deftly explore the hurdles faced by newly independence national, which at times a harsh depiction of reality. These writers have made bold attempts to recapture the altered perceptions of Post – colonial India and the use of revolutionary narrative technique has elevated their position among the writers of Indian Fiction in English.

Role of Indian Women Writers in Diaspora Writing

Women writers in India are moving forward with their strong and sure strides, matching the pace of the world. We see them bursting out in full bloom spreading their own individual fragrances.

They are recognized for their originality, versatility and the indigenous flavor of the soil that they bring to their work. Indian women writers like, Bharathi Mukherjee, Anita Desai, Nayantara Saghla and many more played a pioneering role in conveying the readers a wild range of indigenous Indian issues, punctuated by a strong feministic outlook.

These two women writers of Indian descent, who unconsciously compete with each other in their own realms. Of course, there are scholars who, across the globe, have had attempted to explore various aspects of diaspora writers especially Jhumpa Lahiri and Kiran Desai and this attempt to critically investigate the oeuvre of the pre-eminent women authors having different backgrounds and journeying in different directions but having crucial similarities while dealing with the elements of diaspora demand the attention of the readers and require a significant critical approach to their works of art.

Aims and Objectives of Desai and Lahiri

1. The present research attempts to evaluate the features of diasporic female writers Kiran Desai and Jhumpa Lahiri after a comprehensive evaluation of their works.
2. The Scholar aims to compare Kiran Desai with Jhumpa Lahiri.
3. How these two women diasporic writers have explored their sense of displacement.
4. How they have given more poignancy to the exploration by dealing not only with a geographical dislocation but also socio-cultural sense of displacement.
5. Do the characters of the diasporic writers reflect a sense of dislocation and yearning for their home-land?
6. To identify the similarities of themes and characters between these two most representative Indian Diaspora writers. And to know how near is Kundanika in her treatment to lady characters.
7. What are the similarities and dissimilarities in the writing styles, themes and plots and women characters of the three selected writers?
8. How some of the Diasporic theories find true representation in plot, themes, characterization and style of these writers.

Select Diasporic Themes in Jhumpa Lahiri

The themes discussed, in the works of Lahiri, are most importantly clash of cultures, a sense of alienation, sense of loneliness, an exploration of violence, cultural heritage and homeland, motif and symbols. Next, violence in modern society has become a norm especially the state violence which normally invisible to the naked eyes but pervasive everywhere. As, in the modern and digital era, market – driven commercialization is the norm which normally help boost the wealthy people and affect only the downtrodden, morally conscious people gang together to oppose this move and start a movement to save themselves and save the poorer people from the iron clutches of the state. Lahiri prudently brings out this invisible force and the power of state and the inability of individual souls. In this story, while on a honeymoon to Ireland, Subhash and Elise visit a circle of stones in the countryside, and seeing the flooding all around them, Subhash is reminded of the lowland. In general, there is always no dearth of mentioning of heritage and homeland in the fictional works of Lahiri. Every story – be it a short story or full length novel – Lahiri never fails to remind the readers especially Indian readers about the immigrant features as being felt by the Indian immigrants who live in two worlds.

Analysis of Kiran Desai

The sense of alienation is a pervading theme in any immigrant writings as this emotion is inherent and innate to every human being the moment he starts his journey to the unknown lands and settles

there leaving his siblings and relatives back at home. In the writings of Kiran Desai too, this is being reflected. The theme of alienation has been recurrent in the Indian English fiction. It has become a major concern for post-modern writers and Kiran Desai, daughter of Anita Desai is no exception. She has explored this contemporary issue in her second novel. The Inheritance of Loss for which she took eight long years to complete. The various themes which are intertwined in the novel. The Inheritance of Loss are globalization, multiculturalism, insurgency, poverty, isolation and issues related to loss of identity.

Select Themes in Kiran Desai's Works

The themes in the fictional works of Kiran Desai are varied and in consonance with the Diasporic characteristics, she takes up almost all nuances of immigrant life, its obstacles and the hope for the future. The major themes are sense of loss, contemporary global issues of multiculturalism, economic inequality, fundamentalism, terrorism, postcolonial chaos, challenge of assimilation, comic joy, nationhood, conflicting desires, modernity, increasingly interconnected world, realism, identity – crisis, love and hate, past are present, and dislocation. Furthermore, she deals with the tragedies of the freed third world countries, exile, American dream, power hierarchy, homecoming, loneliness, truth and untruth, cultural identity, class-system, ethnicity, racism, cultural clash, loneliness, and the way of life of westernized Indians. Particularly, the predominant themes in Inheritance of Loss are cultural clash, loneliness, westernized Indians, immigrants.

A Comparative and Contrastive Study of the Works of Desai and Lahiri

The various diaspora elements in the literary works of Jhumpa Lahiri and Kiran Desai for a comparative and contrastive study in terms of diaspora features, themes and how they deal with them. It must be noted that the word 'diaspora' has already become almost a trendy concept and a genre throughout the academic world, is not losing its luster because of the incessant movement of peoples from one country, region, or continent to another for a variety of reasons: economic, political, social and cultural. The convergence of nation and state has brought to a new phenomena such as people belonging to no nations as immigrants are mingling with interracial and intercultural. Now the situation is evolving and converging to a place where the societies of most countries are becoming multiethnic, multicultural, multiracial, and pluralistic.

More Similarities Between Lahiri and Desai

Further more, one could find the following similarities in their works of art:

1. As for the generational gap is concerned, both Lahiri and Desai belong to the 21st century representing the Immigrants as they themselves are immigrants.
2. Both the women writers are outstandingly master storytellers.
3. Winners of various critically acclaimed prizes across the globe, Lahiri has been receiving many world renowned awards including Pulitzer prize given to fictional works written exclusively by American writers. Lahiri was also short listed for the Man Booker Prize for the novel. The Lowland.
4. Kiran Desai also started her career by winning the coveted. Betty award and continued to win the coveted prize the Man. Booker Prize for Inheritance of Loss.
5. Lahiri and Desai share common concerns in their writings by virtue of them both being contemporary female Diaspora writers.
6. One of the important connecting features of these two women writers is sharing of post-colonial links through India. While Lahiri was born in London and relocated to the United States, Desai was born in America but both of them close connection with their native country India.

7. And both the writers share a persisting empathy for their fictional creations.
8. Make the readers connect with the story.
9. Jhumpa Lahiri and Kiran Desai themselves are both Diasporas who Have had to balance their identity between two countries.
10. In their fictional works, the two writers have humanist themes and concerns such as Dialogises of cultural encounters, diaspora, minority discourse, race and other issues.
11. A psychoanalytic introspection into the tormented psyche in their characters.
12. Both of them explores the cross-cultural experiences of dislocated women and the possible condition of belonging simultaneously – psychologically experientially in the maize of cultural plurality.
13. The two women writers deal with the issues of identity and cultural clashed have already been vastly explored in her novels which are crux of the fictional works.
14. Lahiri and Desai explore the issue of cultural encounter specifically.
15. From the perspective of women's identity and her approach to this issue is via feminist literary theory but it is natural.

Conclusion

Considered as one of the eminent voices in the present times articulating the maladies of the people situated in the unaccustomed earth of the Diaspora communities, Lahiri's narratives focus mainly on the itineraries of her subjects, especially, her female characters, facilitating them to explore their ethnicities, identities and femininities. Diasporic identities, multiple migrations, shift in locations and mobility make the female characters more free and liberate that their home country. Women play important roles in diaporic experience. In both stories, Jhumpa Lahiri and Kiran Desai reveals the negotiation process when diasporic people are faced the in betweenness situation. Both old and new world are important since the new world is the world where people must adapt to new environment and inevitably run from some social structures of it. It is the women who play a lot in the negotiation process and select values that may not be suit to old world.

References

1. Cohen, Robin. *Global Diaspora : An Introduction*. New York ; Routledge, 2008.
2. Vertovec, Steven . "Three Meanings of 'Diaspora', Exemplified among South Asian Religions. "University of Oxford , 29 August 2012.
3. R.K Singh's master pieces of Indian English Writers " A Critical Study".
4. Nithyanandam Indira Jhumpa Lahiri " The Tile of Diaspora, Delhi Centric Book 2008 Printed".